

CLEWs based on Democratic Republic of Congo's NDC for a Sustainable Development

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This study focuses on the implications of implementing the laws adopted in the NDCs of the Democratic Republic of the Congo, in the field of agriculture and also in the field of energy, based on Climate, Land, Energy and Water Systems. Through this CLEWs modeling exercise using the OSeMOSYS tool, we developed 3 scenarios, baseline, food security and electrification, to assess their impacts on land use, emissions and water demand.

The baseline has given us an energy generation mainly consisting of coal. Other energy generation mix include hydroelectric power, solar energy and natural gas. Land use was mainly forest, followed by agricultural use and Water balance.

For food security scenario, the result showed that for the same body production, less land is required if the irrigated land area is increased by 185%, thus preserving the forest. Lastly, for the electrification scenario, the result showed low CO₂ production, investment in renewable energy is required, thus contributing to the electrification of the territory.

Therefore, we recommend that in order to increase food security, the DRC should invest in and prioritize irrigation farming, which provides good production efficiency, i.e. high production for the same area of land. This would make up for the shortfall in agricultural feed while preserving the forest as much as possible. Additionally, for electrification, to better serve the population and produce less CO₂, we recommend that the DRC invest in renewable energy and, with limits, in non-renewable energy.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) is a country with a surface area of 2345409 km², with an estimated population of 91946513 in 2021, and a growth rate of 3.4 to 4%. It is one of the world's largest freshwater reserves, ranked 16th in Africa, and represents 10 percent of the world's tropical forest reserves and 50 % of Africa's dense forests.

The DRC has a vast energy potential, of which the hydroelectric potential alone (the Congo River, not to mention other rivers) is estimated at 100,000 MW, which would represent 37% of Africa's total potential, as well as 6% of the world's potential. The DRC is endowed with enormous energy potential, including biomass, solar, wind, uranium, and geothermal energy. Despite all this potential, the DRC faces a number of challenges, including access to electricity and poverty.

According to the DRC's revised National Determined Commitment (NDC), the rate of access to electricity has been estimated at 9%, and only a quarter of the population has reached food security. The NDC also identifies access to electricity and food security as key indicators of development. On the other hand, the challenge is to achieve development with low CO₂ emissions.

This introduces our research question, which is

What are the strategies required to increase access to food and electricity with lower CO₂ Emissions in the Democratic Republic of Congo?

In this work, we will try to answer this question through 3 scenarios: The baseline scenario through which we tried to imitate the current situation of the DRC, the food security scenario where we increased the agricultural production and the electrification scenario, where we adopted a better formula for emitting less CO₂.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this research, the CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) framework was applied using the OSeMOSYS (Open Source Energy Modelling System) tool. While OSeMOSYS was originally developed for energy systems analysis, its functionality and flexibility permit its adaptation to the integrated analysis of CLEWs. This approach facilitates a comprehensive assessment of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, enabling a whole systems approach to decision-making (Ramos et al., 2022).

The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit for DRC served as the baseline model, incorporating the reference energy system developed by Cannone and Allington (2021). Additionally, agriculture and water data were sourced from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and International Energy Agency (IEA) databases.

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Three Scenarios were developed:

a. Baseline

Energy production is dominated by coal (over 80%), solar (10%) and the remainder by hydroelectricity and natural gas. Most of the land is forest, followed by agricultural land, then water and finally built-up areas, estimated at 1% of the total surface area. Half of the Water Balance portion is occupied by precipitation, followed by evapotranspiration, water surface and groundwater. More than 99% of baseline emissions come from the energy sector, in the order of 2000 million tons

b. Food Security

This scenario is based on increasing agricultural productivity. The area currently equipped with irrigation equipment is 5% of the total cultivated area in the DRC, i.e. 350,000 ha irrigated out of a total of 7,000,000 ha. In the DRC's NCD, one of the indicators for increasing agricultural production is to raise the irrigated area to 1,000,000 ha, which corresponds to 185%. Based on our scenario, the irrigated area would increase by 185%.

c. Electrification

This scenario is based on reducing CO₂ emissions. As the DRC is a country seeking its own path to development, we have opted for a mix of renewable and non-renewable types of energy.

3. RESULTS

We have explored the results through three different scenarios as shown in the successive sections

Using these graphs, we will make a comparative analysis between the Baseline and Food Security, and then between the Baseline and Electrification.

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3.1 Comparison of Baseline and Food Security Scenarios

Fig 1: Area by land cover type

Fig 2: Crop by production

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Fig 3: Agriculture imports for baseline scenario

In the baseline line scenario, we can see on Figure 1 the dominance of forest in the Area by Land Cover Type figure, which gradually decreases over time until 2050, when it becomes almost flat with the increase in cultivated area. The model represents the evolution of cultivated area over time, which depends on population growth (3.29% per year). In this model, the ratio between the rainfed and the irrigated yields is 0.07%.

For the baseline, the need to import crops is felt from the year 2056 onwards, the year in which land occupation by crops loses its slope. The slope becomes flat as a result of the imposition made on the model to preserve half of the land occupation, and prefers to meet the demand for crops by import.

In the food security scenario, the portion of land used for agriculture decreases in size in this scenario (40% less than in the Baseline) in 2040 to the benefit of the forest as shown in Figure 2. It can be seen in figure 3 that for the same crop production, the irrigation technique would use less surface area. In addition to this, our import crop graph is empty for the Food Security Scenario. If we capture the Water balance of this two Scenarios, we will notice a slight increase (by 0.4 billion of m³) in water demand in the Food Security Scenario, for the same production.

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Baseline

Food Security

Fig 4: Water demand by scenario

3.2. Comparison of Baseline and Electrification scenarios

Fig 5: Power generation by scenario

It should be noted that 80% of energy is generated by Power Coal, 10% by solar and the remainder by Hydro and Natural Gas. This has resulted in high CO2 emissions, but a relatively small capital investment. In the Electrification Scenario, on the other hand, we see a much more even split between Biomass and Coal. Solar and Hydro supplement the rest of the energy demand.

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Fig 6: CO₂ annual emission by scenario

Fig 7: Total capital investment by scenario

If we compare the two scenarios, we see that the baseline scenario emits more CO₂ than the electrification scenario, but at a lower cost, while the electrification Scenario emits less CO₂, but at a much higher investment cost as shown in Figure 6 and Figure 7.

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4. DISCUSSION

The Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) approach to integrated systems management emerges as a valuable tool, offering a holistic analysis that extends beyond climate considerations to encompass the integration of energy, land and water systems. This whole systems perspective becomes especially pertinent as these systems are inherently interconnected, highlighting the importance of considering their collective impact.

This tool gives us an idea of how land use would evolve with irrigation techniques. In this modelling exercise, it is important to emphasize that the various parameters influencing agriculture are considered to be uniform throughout the DRC.

However, it must be stressed that the cultivation and drying coefficients of all crops are not the same throughout the DRC, let alone the productivity of the land in the DRC.

In a much more practical approach, the use of precise parameters would give a much more detailed apperception of the evolution of land use as well as the interconnection between water, climate and irrigation.

On the other hand, as far as the electrification scenario is concerned, the baseline has rather considered a least-cost situation, which does not exactly reflect the energy situation in the DRC.

It is also important to acknowledge the limitations that apply to this exercise, which relies on a simplified reference energy system (RES) for DRC. The model, while informative, does not encompass the full spectrum of energy, land and water systems. Consequently, the insights developed offer a partial view of the implications and potentials associated with different pathways. Recognizing these constraints leads to opportunities of future research that builds upon this foundation, expanding the model to provide a more faithful representation of DRC's complex energy, land and water systems.

5. CONCLUSION

This study explored both the transition of energy technologies and the transition of agricultural technologies in the Democratic Republic of Congo. This research has enabled us to understand the importance of using a much more integrated approach to decision-making and legislation.

After analyzing the three scenarios Baseline, Food Security and Electrification, we understood the consequences each technique would have on water, land use and climate. Based on the results, we will encourage the adoption of intensive irrigation methods for crop production and investment in mixed energy (renewable and non-renewable, to strike a balance between investment and CO2 emissions).

As a recommendation to future CLEWs Modelers for the Democratic Republic of Congo, we suggest analyzing the impact that exploiting all the hydroelectric potential would have, given that the DRC is considered internationally as a solution country, thanks to these natural resources

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